

Modeling Sun photosphere granulation as a boiling process

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Abstract. In this paper I try to extract typical Sun photosphere granule sizes and then map it to the boiling process in the liquids using Reynolds number definition. So that if granules would be formed as some sort of plasma bubbles formation and flow, what would be the requirements of such “boiling” process?

Extracting typical granule area from segmentation

From wikipedia given Sun granulation image,

I have performed image segmentation in Julia programming language with such algorithm :

```
using Images, ImageSegmentation, Random, Statistics
function get_random_color(seed)
    Random.seed!(seed)
    return rand(RGB{N0f8})
end
km2_per_pixel = (36500^2)/(1024^2);
img = load("granularity.jpg");
bw = Gray(img) .< 0.5;
dist = 1 .- distance_transform(feature_transform(bw));
markers = label_components(dist .< -5);
segments = watershed(dist, markers);
counts = collect(values(segment_pixel_count(segments)));
counts = filter((x) -> x >= 50, counts);
areas = map((x) -> x * km2_per_pixel, counts);
avg = mean(areas);
dev = std(areas);
print("Mean: ", trunc(Int, avg), " km^2", "\nStd deviation: ", trunc(Int, dev), "\n");
img = (map(i->get_random_color(i), labels_map(segments)) .* (1 .- bw));
save("segmented.jpg", img);
```

Then segmented blobs of granules were detected which could be seen in output image :

My algorithm also has calculated average granule area which was approximately about 1.2 million km^2 , - comparable to the South Africa area. Standard deviation of areas was pretty high, about 900 000 km^2 , so rule “one size fit’s them all” clearly does not apply to plasma granulation process, or in other words it does not follow normal distribution law at least in sharp form. Wikipedia gives typical granule diameter of 1500 km, so this fact extrapolated to a circle area would give 1.7 million km^2 . Thus, my granule area calculations corresponds to a wikipedia reference within 30% relative error, which is quite good given that segmentation algorithm may have errors and inconsistencies too.

Using Reynolds number for modeling bubble flow in plasma

One using Reynolds number and plasma flow characteristics, can predict bubble diameter :

$$D_b = \frac{Re \cdot \mu}{\rho u} \quad 1$$

, where μ is fluid dynamic viscosity, ρ - density of fluid and u bubble flow speed. Sun photosphere density is about 0.2 g/m^3 . Sun interior has huge Reynolds numbers about 10^9 . And for photosphere viscosity we can substitute $4.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Substituting all this data into (1) formula and assuming that bubble flow to surface speed would be 160 m/s , one would get about such bubble diameter which would correspond to my calculated granule area of 1.2 million square kilometers. Granule area could be interpreted as plasma bubble cross-section. So if granules were to be formed by some kind of “plasma boiling” process, then these plasma bubbles must be able to reach Sun surface at high 160 m/s speeds.

Conclusions. With image segmentation it was concluded that average Sun granule area is about 1.2 million km^2 having standard deviation of $\sim 900 \text{ 000 } km^2$. From Reynolds number formula (1) it was deduced that if plasma granules were to be formed by some process of bubbles formation and flowing to the surface,- then these bubbles must be traveling with moderate 160 m/s velocities.